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Growing Chinese Involvement in West Asia: Factors and Implications

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Abstract:

China is an emerging power in the world and its influence in West Asian region is increasing rapidly. Since communists took over China, it maintained a good relationship with several countries in the region and now Beijing which has only friends and no enemy there, is seen as a competitor to US hegemony. Its rising economy, military power, market productivity and the so-called non-interventionist approach have given leverage to engage more with West Asian countries. Since China's iconic project Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) was announced, its expectations from these countries have increased. Beijing's ambitions in West Asia are not limited to only oil, gas and market but the region also has a strategic importance and BRI includes all such aspects. The region is also very important because it comes between the Asia and Europe where Asia is known as the largest manufacturing region in the world in which China holds the key position and Europe and Africa are the important destinations for exporters. China's trade and investment will be affected massively by any instability in the region and it will also affect its maritime activity and exports to Europe and Africa. Apart from the economic front, China is very much involved in the strategic issues of the region. It also has good relations with both Iran and Saudi Arabia and increasing its non-combatant presence in crises like the Syrian civil war. The aim of this chapter is to explain and explore

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China's interest in the region and its impact on the region and global politics.

Keywords: *China, West Asia, Belt and Road Initiative, BRI*

China's involvement in the region has multiple dimensions including historical, economic, cultural and geo-political interests. In recent times, China's interests in this region have been increased due to the region's importance for its energy needs, a vast market, and its geographical location connecting Africa and Europe through the sea route. It is evident that since the BRI was announced in 2013 by President Xi Jinping, China's expectations from these countries have increased. It believes that these nations can play a vital role to facilitate the BRI-related projects. Chinese ambitions in West Asia can be identified as seeking energy security, economic gain through the big market in the region, providing logistics to the BRI and sea route trade, strengthening military relations and relations with the overseas Chinese diaspora.

In the history of China- West Asia relation, the Bandung Conference of 1955 and Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence or Panchsheel are very important. The Bandung Conference in Indonesia where representatives of 29 countries from Asia and Africa were gathered had given an opportunity to leaders of China and Arab countries to meet and share their ideas. It also played a crucial role in the future for economic, cultural and even in the diplomatic relations with these countries¹

Panchsheel has importance for all international relations but more for China and Arab countries because they are so different from each other in terms of society, culture, political structure and these principles of mutual coexistence were important to engage more with the region.

Though countries like Saudi Arabia were a hesitant for a long period of time to establish formal diplomatic relations with PRC but countries such as Egypt, Syria and Yemen had taken lead to establish relations soon after the Bandung Conference. Arab

nations support one China policy propagated by the PRC and in 1971 during the UN resolution on the same, two third of Arab countries voted in the favour of PRC.

² Traditionally, China support Palestine issue and rarely comment on internal issue of the Arab world. The nature of governing systems and governance in the Arab world suit more to China and its own style of government and that allow both to maintain secrecy on major policies and agreements from the both sides. Contrary to it, the US has been accused of selling and forcing democracy to the Arab world and put demands of policy change on social and political issues but there is hardly any such thing from Beijing. Though Arab countries are known as traditional allies of the US, but Beijing is working to involve more and more with them and trying to promote consistency on the issue of One China policy.

Since the post reform in China, its involvement in the region has increased but it didn't speed up due to the cold war. The post-cold war era has witnessed more close relationship between China and various Arab nations including Saudi Arabia which established diplomatic relations in 1990. Since then and especially in the 21th century there is surge of not only trade volume but high-level official visits too and it is instrumental to boost cooperation among them. While meeting with the then Secretary General of Arab League Amr Musa and a delegation of 22-member states of Arab League in 2004, Chinese President Hu Jintao has proposed four principles for developing relations between China and Arab world. Later on, the China-Arab Cooperation Forum was established in 2004 and that was a new chapter in the dynamics of China-West Asia relations in the 21th century.³

Important of China West Asia Relations

China's need for energy is vast and it is increasing rapidly. Beijing's economic growth is more or less depended on energy namely oil and gas and China imports a large amount oil & gas from West Asia. Due to the massive production and economic

growth the demand of oil and gas is increasing in China. Beijing imported crude oil worth more than 82 billion USD from the region in 2020.⁴ Countries like Saudi Arabia, Iraq, Oman, UAE, Kuwait and Iran are among the biggest oil exporters to China.⁵ One of the main factors of BRI is to secure access to energy in various part of the world. Two third of all the crude oil imported into China comes from the West Asian and African countries; there is always a possibility to increase the volume further. The issue of energy security is very important for any country and so for China and any disturbance in the region will affect not only its supply line but also its growth in the long run. Developing the Maritime Silk Road is the other component of the BRI and purports to connect nations across the world through the sea routes.

The ancient sea route of communication which connected East Asian countries, including China, to West Asia, Africa and Europe is being upgraded by China under the BRI. Beijing plans to invest a huge amount of money in the 21st Century Maritime Silk Road and hopes that it will connect countries of the multiple continents and will benefit them economically. Trade through shipping is known as cheapest compare to other modes of transportation and according to China's official data, its foreign trade is almost 90 percent dependent on shipping. For the same purpose China is developing a number of ports in the region. China also perceives West Asia as a big construction market. It is expected that global construction market will increase, requiring huge investment and labour force, which will provide opportunity to global construction companies, including those from China. The reconstruction works in Yemen, Syria, Iraq and Libya will also require investment and provide work opportunities.

China is also emerging as a military power and is increasing its capacity in various forms. It has an operational naval base in Djibouti. China will be an influential power in terms of selling weapons and state of the art technologies to the West Asian nations, which the US and some western countries are hesitant to

sell. In the long run, China will be a competitor to the US and other western countries in arms trade. In 2016, Chinese President Xi Jinping in his speech before the Arab League in Cairo, explained Beijing's role in West Asia saying, "Instead of looking for a proxy in the Middle East, we promote peace talks; instead of seeking any sphere of influence, we call on all parties to join the circle of friends for the Belt and Road Initiative; instead of attempting to fill the "vacuum," we build a cooperative partnership network for win-win outcomes."⁶

Since its formation, Communist China has adopted a policy of political 'non-interference' in West Asia. However, in the last few years, this claim is facing multiple challenges. China established its first overseas naval base in Djibouti. The base was opened on the day of People's Liberation Army (PLA)'s 90th birth anniversary on July 30, 2019. China released its first 'Arab Policy Paper' in January 2016 and soon after appointed a special envoy for Syrian crisis. In March 2017 China signed an agreement with Saudi Arabia to manufacture Chinese drones in the Kingdom. It will be the first such Chinese manufacturing unit in West Asia. China also tries to balancing between Iran and Saudi Arabia. Since the Syrian crisis emerged in 2011, China voted seven times along with Russia in the United Nations in favour of Syria's Basharal-Assad regime, significantly, unlike its vote on Libya.

The presence of the US and its role in the polity, economics and security of the region is another important factor for China to face there. Traditionally most the counties in the region are known for its strong relation with Washington but since the past few decades they want to engage well with Beijing too. Apart from economic reasons they want to balance the US pressure and to compel him to do more for them.⁷ Also, China's political system doesn't need much ifs and buts and approval from within its political and bureaucratic system compared to the western democracies and it speed up any deal especially arms sales to such countries otherwise it has to go through various check and balances that may include parliament, judiciary and sometimes media

criticism.⁸ In the region and other parts of the world China is known for its 'wolf warrior diplomacy' which focuses on securing and strengthening the existing allies or potential allies and pushing back to all those countries that ally with US in its anti-China efforts.⁹ Though on the pragmatic side nothing is going to change on the ground but considering the nature of authoritarian regime in a number of countries in the region, Chinese diplomatic advancement and vocabulary are more convincing and influential compared to the US.¹⁰ China's growth after the economic reform and especially in the 21st century and the kind of political stability create a kind of attraction of the so called Chinese model in region where somehow similar authoritarianism is in place.¹¹

West Asia's strategic importance

The strategic importance of the West Asian region is an established factor for various reasons not for China but for all major powers in the world. Geographically, it comes between the Asia and Europe where Asia is known as the largest manufacturing region in the world in which China hold the key position and Europe and Africa is the important destinations for exporters. World's 14 percent trade goods and China's 60 percent export to Europe only go through Suez Canal.¹² Therefore, as a part of China's maritime strategy, now the Suez Canal Corridor is getting massive investment from Chinese shipping companies to build ports. Beijing's trade and investment will be affected massively by any instability in the region and it will also affect its maritime activity and exports to Europe and Africa.

China has diplomatic and friendly relations with all countries in the region and despite rivalries like Saudi Arabia with Iran it is regarded as a friend of all and enemy of none. Due to various reasons including foreign interventions, rich in energy and being the one of the most important strategic locations, the region is often caught into the conflict and that worry China. Therefore, over the years, Beijing has developed a habit to be ready with its non-combatant forces for a rescue operation of its citizens from

the region. During the Arab spring China rescued 1800 citizens from Egypt and 2000 from Syria and 30,000 during the Libyan war.¹³ During the war in Libya in 2011, China suffered a loss of \$18.8 billion when a number of trade routes were affected.¹⁴

China's concern is not limited to only these traditional conflicts but the emergence of militant groups like ISIS makes the situation more complex. There have been a few incidents where Chinese cargos were hit by such groups in the Suez Canal in 2013. Therefore, any disturbance in the region will pose a direct threat to Chinese's ambition of its Maritime Silk Road. Beijing is also active in the Gulf of Aden for its anti-piracy mission in the Arabian Seas. China's first overseas naval base has already become functional in Djibouti where about 10,000 military personal can be stationed. This base is for anti-terror activities, humanitarian assistant and disaster relief.¹⁵

China's Economic Involvement in the Region

China's economic involvements in the region are very crucial and have the key of its engagement in West Asia. For last few decades, China's capabilities in higher technology have witnessed a massive growth and through it Beijing got more opportunities in the third world and that is not only limited to supply and production but it also motivates those nations for cooperation in various fields. It also gives them an alternate of the so-called US hegemony in various parts of the world including West Asia. Due to its rich natural resources of oil and gas, countries in the West Asian region have another advantage while trading with China. While Arab countries import huge amount of goods and commodities from China but the balance of trade is more or less in favour of them because of their exports of oil and gas. As far as the bilateral trade is concerned, China and the West Asia recorded US\$ 330 billion bilateral trade in 2021.¹⁶ Beijing has invested some \$200 billion in West Asia in the last 15 years.¹⁷ Beijing's commercial activities in region are a bit vast and not limited to oil and gas only. China is also the biggest exporter for the region. It exports goods like Chemicals, clothing, electronics, food

products, grain, light industrial equipment, metal, minerals, oil and textiles. Exports from West Asian countries to China include goods like aluminium, chemicals, copper, fertilizer, oil and steel. In 2019 trade between Saudi Arabia and China reached \$76 billion and till 2021 China has been the largest trading partner of the Kingdom.¹⁸ The Kingdom is also the biggest crude oil supplier to China.¹⁹ On the investment side, region's oil and gas or energy sector got primary focus from Beijing but it is also involved in various sectors and contracts related to infrastructure projects for Chinese companies and marketing for other products in the region. From the period of 2005-2017, the WANA region got a total of 12 percent China's overseas investment that is US\$207 billion.²⁰ China's investment in West Asia was only 1\$ billion about a decade ago but it is booming now. According to a report prepared by the Green Finance & Development Center at Fudan University in 2021 under BRI China's investment in Araba and West Asian countries increased 360 percent compared to 2020.²¹ In 2018 Beijing promised to invest 23\$ billion as development aid and loan during the ministerial meeting of China-Arab States Cooperation Forum (CASCF).²²

Saudi Arabia got the biggest share of Chinese investment in the 2005-2017 period which is a US\$30.18 billion and it is 15 percent of total amount invested by China in WANA region.²³ In the 2017 visit, King Salam bin Abdulaziz and President Xi Jinping have signed a MoU of US\$65 billion²⁴. And in the same year Beijing and Tel Aviv have signed the China-Israel Innovative Comprehensive Partnership. The bilateral trade reached from \$50 million in 1992 to \$22.8 billion in 2021.²⁵

Belt and Road Initiative and West Asia

The Belt and Road Initiative or BRI has a very broad, vibrant and inclusive framework which has a number of sub frameworks within. It covers a mixture of a large number of ongoing, planned and upcoming infrastructure projects based on various bilateral, multilateral and regional agreements. The main objective of the

BRI is to connect China with the rest of the world through a large network of highways, railroads, transport corridors, sea routes, ports, energy pipelines and communication infrastructures. BRI is divided in two parts. One is land route called “Silk Road Economic Belt” and the other one is the sea route known as “21st Century Maritime Silk Road”. Actually, it is China’s long-term development strategy of not only the connectivity across the globe but through it China wants to access the global market in the larger scale to sell its developmental strategy aiming to be a global power to counter hegemonic powers. It will also make easy for China to access world’s resources stretched across the continents, create new markets, help China to export its production without hassles with a lower transportation cost and internationalise RMB, the Chinese currency. West Asia is one of the important regions for the BRI. Since China announced BRI project, countries in the West Asian region have warmly welcomed and promised for cooperation.²⁶ As an emerging power with an ambition to be a superpower, China also wants its strong presence there if not competition with other powers and BRI only increase China’s interest in the region from all these and other aspects.²⁷

In 2014, President Xi Jinping in the inaugural session of the 6th China-Arab States Cooperation Forum said that friendship and mutual understanding are there between China and West Asian countries since the ancient Silk Road and they are natural allies in the journey of BRI. He stressed to focus on principles like discussion and cooperation to have a common interest and to build a common destiny. The Arab Policy Paper, which is the first detailed policy document released by the PRC since its establishment during President Xi Jinping’s visit to Arab countries in 2016, says that both China and Arab countries will work together under the guiding principle of “wide consultation, joint contribution and shared benefit”. It also talks about energy, infrastructure construction and new technologies.²⁸

Countries in the West Asian region are sharpening their edge for more industrial growth and it is evident from their planned projects and SEZs. Projects like Vision 2030 of Saudi Arabia, Vision 2020 of Oman and Jordan's Vision 2025 are some example of the same. Thus, there are a number of new opportunities available for investors and high-tech people and China is very much involved in most of these projects. Apart from Saudi Arabia, there are other Arab countries who want to get out their dependency on oil-based economy. These countries are also eager to renewable energy and information industry.²⁹ Countries like Egypt, Israel, Turkey, UAE and others are planning to invest in massive housing projects, new roadways and high-speed rail networks. Gulf railway network or the GCC Railway that will connect distance of 2177 km distance of Gulf states from Kuwait to Oman is already under construction and expected to complete by 2023.³⁰ Egypt, the first country which recognized PRC in the region, is one of the most important pivots of the BRI in the region where some 86 Chinese companies have invested more than \$1.1 billion in the new Suez Canal Economic Zone making China one of the largest foreign investor.³¹ Through BRI China is strengthening its foot in the energy sector of the region. Apart from oil and gas it is working on the renewable energy like solar, wind and other forms in the region. Arab countries including Saudi Arabia are also interested to work with China to explore the possibility to develop nuclear energy for peaceful purpose.

China's Balancing Approach with Saudi Arabia, Iran and Israel

Saudi Arabia

Sino-Saudi relation is among the newest in the West Asia. Both countries have started engaging with each other diplomatically from 1990. Since then it grows rapidly and steadily. From trade to cultural cooperation, high level visits and not intervening each other's domestic affairs-- at all fronts Sino-Saudi relations can be termed as well-oiled and well going. Saudi Arabia has 18 percent

of total oil reserve in the world and in 2009 China replaced the US as the biggest importer of oil from the Kingdom.³² China imports significant amount of oil from Saudi Arabia which is about 20 percent of its total import³³ and it is more compared to Iran as well which exports about 6 percent of its total import.³⁴ Since last two decades bilateral visits including head of states have been increased. President Xi Jinping visited Arab counties in 2016. A joint venture has been initiated in the oil refinery sector between Saudi Arabian Oil Company Aramco and the China Petroleum and Chemical Corporation (Sinopec). The initiative is known as Yanbu Aramco Sinopec Refining Company (YASREF) which was inaugurated in 2016 during the visit of President Xi Jinping's visit to the Kingdom. Originally it was started in 2012 with \$10 billion investment from China where Sinopec has 37 percent shares.³⁵ In the same year during the King Salman's visit to Beijing both countries have signed 15 agreements ranging from energy, finance, housing, infrastructure, mining and public works sectors.³⁶ A year later Saudi King Salman bin Abdul Aziz's and in 2019 Saudi Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman's visit to Beijing was also well received.

Apart from trade, China is also diversifying its security engagement as in 2017 it has signed an agreement with Saudi Arabia to manufacture Chinese drones in the Kingdom. Recently both countries have established a company namely Aerial Solutions to proceed it further.³⁷ It will be the first such Chinese manufacturing unit in West Asia. Beijing is also helping Saudi Arabia in the field of nuclear energy. In August 2017 Saudi Geological Survey signed a memorandum of understanding with China's state-run China National Nuclear Corp in this regard.³⁸ Tourism is another important sector where both countries other West Asian countries are benefiting each other. Saudi Railways Organization has awarded a contract worth 160 million Saudi Riyal to China Railway Construction Corp to upgrade second phase of the 91 km of the Dammam – Riyadh freight line³⁹. China has signed agreements related to promotion of tourism with

several countries in the region and major cities have direct flight connectivity with China.

Iran

China is known as Iran's all-weather friend. For Tehran, China is one of the most important countries which are strategic hedge against the US hegemony. Its economy, military power, industrial growth and future prospects are steady compared to any developed country or the power of the world. Beijing-Tehran partnership at least has three important components. One is its energy resources which is necessary for industrial functioning and growth of China. Second; Tehran's strategic activism against the US which makes Iran many times a natural ally of Beijing in the region. Third is, Iran plays a leading role in the Shiite community and it matters for countries like Syria, Lebanon, Iraq etc.

The bilateral trade was only \$440 million in 1996 that reached \$50 billion in 2013 and in 2016 both countries have agreed to take China-Iran trade up to \$600 billion in 10 years.⁴⁰ Beijing is the biggest importer of Iranian oil that is one third of Iran's total exports. China is also a major market for non-oil commodities of Iran that was 21 percent in 2016. Since last eight years, about 30 percent of Iran's foreign trade was done with China. Beijing is also one of the biggest foreign investors for Tehran.⁴¹ As Beijing considers energy as core in its involvement in the West Asia, BRI will provide massive opportunity for investment in Iran's energy sector. In 2017, after the implementation of the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA), a \$4.879 billion contract was signed between the China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC) and National Iranian Oil Company to develop 11th phase of South Pars Gas Field. After the US pulled out from JCPOA, Iran announced to hand over total share to CNPC.⁴² China has been one of the important exporters of weapons to Iran.⁴³ As a part of BRI, China is also investing heavily in the development of transportation projects and playing important role in the

electrification of Tehran Mashhad Railway and the Tehran-Qom-Isfahan High-Speed Rail Projects.⁴⁴

Israel

Within a few months after the PRC was established in October 1, 1949, Israel was the first country in the region to recognise the new communist regime in China⁴⁵. And a few months later on 19 September 1950 when the issue of PRC's representation came before United Nations, Israel along with other countries favoured PRC against Republic of China (Taiwan) but it wasn't successful then⁴⁶. But later on, especially after the Bandung Conference, China supported Palestinian cause and it was one of the important reasons for not having diplomatic relations with Israel till 1990s. Sino-Israel relations are not on the costs of Sino-US relations as China is important for any country in the world so as for Israel which is said to have many challenges for its so called existence. China has been very much interested in high technology of Israel and Israel has been regarding China as a rising power with the largest population and its track record of massive investment in the country. Economic and trade relation were there even before formal diplomatic relation and both countries were in cooperation in the trade of military equipment. After the Tiananmen Square incident in 1989 when China faced massive criticism from western world and US and its allies imposed sanctions but Israel maintained a very minimal and formal critics and the back-door channel was remained active⁴⁷.

Beijing's affection with Israel's high technology can be understood by the fact that after his visit to Beijing in 2013, Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu told his cabinet that China is interested in "three things: Israeli technology, Israeli technology and Israeli technology".⁴⁸ China's investment is rising in Israel and it was expected that it will overtake the US and the largest investor in the country where high tech sectors including the telecommunication were seen the most important for Beijing and Tel Aviv for cooperation. Tourism is another sector which is

booming and in 2017 at least 46 percent more Chinese tourists visited Israel compared to 2016⁴⁹.

The US is concerned on China's engagement with Israel because through it China will be able to access Israel's sensitive information regarding internal security and various databases and that won't be good for latter's national security in the long run and also it will be dangerous for the US also because Chinese companies are being involved in some projects which has direct connection with US forces such as the Haifa port⁵⁰ where US naval forces come once in every year. Amid the whole world was facing the outbreak of COVID19 pandemic, U.S. Secretary of State Mike Pompeo paid an official visit to Tel Aviv in May 2020 and one of the most important agenda of the visit was to pressurise Israel to cancel the deal in which the Chinese company the Shanghai International Port Group (SIPG) which was given permission to operate a terminal in the strategically significant Port of Haifa. The SIPG has built a terminal in Haifa Port and will operate for 25 five years. But Washington was not happy with this deal and pushing Tel Aviv to reconsider its decision.⁵¹ Finally, the port was inaugurated in September last year. Apart from this, it was expected that the contract of Sorek 2, the world's largest seawater desalination plant will go to Hong Kong-based company Hutchison Water but due to massive pressure from Trump administration it was given to Israel's IDE Technologies⁵². The US had complained so many times against Israeli technology sharing with China⁵³. Israel didn't feel good to withdraw it saying that the authorities in Washington knew about it in advance but didn't pose a clear objection. This is not the first time when Israel has to surrender on the pressure or the US but it happened in the past too.⁵⁴

Due to the US pressure Israel have witnessed many ups and downs as far as the sharing of its technological abilities with China is concerned and in 2019 Tel Aviv established a body to monitor and track foreign investments in the country.⁵⁵ In a recent paper, US based think tank, the Foundation for the Defense of Democracies has urged Washington to work with Tel Aviv and its other allies and facilitate alternates of China⁵⁶. The US is putting such pressures on its other allies in the region and they

face tough choice to deal with it⁵⁷. It seems that in the long run Tel Aviv has to choose either Washington or Beijing.

Rising China is not a myth but a reality and its economic growth, technological advancement and producing capacity are solid proof of it. The whole world acknowledges it and trying to deal with it accordingly. Beijing itself behaves in a very mature way compared to initial years of the PRC. Also, the monarchical government system in most countries of the West Asia suits them and China both to deal more effectively and frequently. Considering economy as core for development and prosperity Beijing's engagement with the West Asian region is increasing and in the one hand it focuses on its exports and bilateral trade and in the other hand it trying to secure its supply of energy from the region. For the same purpose Beijing tries to balance among various stakeholders. It has good relations with both Saudi Arabia and Iran and one of the top trading partners of both. Also, one of the important factors for Saudi Arabia's binding relations with China is that Beijing should not tilt towards Iran more and increasing Sino-Saudi military relation is because of it.⁵⁸ Analysts believe that changing dynamics of world polity has compelled Saudi Arabia to revise and update its foreign policy towards the East Asia therefore for a decade there has been a strategic pivot of the Kingdom towards China. Since then the volume of business, strategic partnership and military alliances have witnessed a change.⁵⁹ Saudi policy makers also see the change in the US influence globally and changing attitude towards West Asia, especially during the period of Barak Obama. Differences over conflicts like Syria and Yemen have added more into them. China's increasing engagement with Iran was another matter of concern and all these compelled the Kingdom to make new partners and broad its foreign policy. China appealed both Iran and Saudi Arabia to resolve their issues with mutual and friendly consultations. In 2017 China signed a deal of \$65 billion with Saudi Arabia and then granted \$10 billion credit line for infrastructure projects to Iran. China also backed Iran for its admission in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization.⁶⁰ China's

engagement and investment in Israel which is neither recognized by Riyadh nor Tehran but known as a close ally of the US, are increasing. For the last couple of years China's investment in Israel's technology is also increasing and experts estimate that China's investment will overtake the US in coming years and this is not a good news for Washington. Israel also supports BRI and one of the founding members of China led Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB).

The question arises that whether increasing Sino-Arab relation poses a challenge to the US hegemony in the region. The answer can be both in affirmative and negative. The increasing trade, bilateral relation, technological support from China to West Asian countries are far ahead compare to two decades ago but can China compete and replace the US in the nearest future is something which cannot be said for sure. Though due to some inconsistent policies of the US, countries in the region sometimes found easy to have a deal with China but the kind of influence and establishment the US has in the region is far from comparison to China and it will take much time for Beijing to challenge Washington and its hegemony in the region.

Although China projects itself as someone who believes the notion of non-interventions but as military power, its presence in the region is increasing. From being a small arm supplier to establishing a drone factory in Saudi Arabia and operating a base in Djibouti, China seems to be assertive and its non-interventionism sometimes are seen as intervention or not letting anyone else to intervene and that is very clear in the case of Syria.

Conclusion

China's engagement in West Asia is very significant and its presence is increasing. It seems that in the nearest future Beijing will have stronger foothold in the region. West Asia is an important region for China and for all major powers in the world. Due to its geographical location, rich energy resources and political dynamics, the region has been contested for many times

in the course of the history and still battling on the same line. As Mao Zedong believed the concept of intermediate zone where the hostile forces trying to assert their presence and capture it, the West Asian region is also among them where world powers always try to influence everything. During the Mao period the PRC has very limited relations with countries in the region and several domestic issues in China including the Great Leap Forward and the Cultural Revolution didn't allow Beijing to focus more on West Asia. After China introduce various reforms and become market economy in 1978, its relation with West Asia and other parts of the world started booming. After the Cold War period these engagements got new beginnings and business got at centre stage in the bilateral trade, official visits and cultural exchanges.

China's BRI project is also important for West Asia. For all such developmental projects the energy is the key and its security will be very challenging for China. The major objectives before Beijing for such a massive project are to enhance energy procurement, secure its supply routes and expedite the supply chain of its exports to the world. For all such purposes China is building ports, railway tracks, highways and SEZs in various parts of the world including West Asia.

Many analysts see China's rise and its engagement in West Asia as a threat to the US. Though it is true that China's engagement in the region has increased substantially it is too early to say that it can uproot the US strong foothold from there because Beijing is hesitant to get involved in various conflicts in the region. Though its noninterventionist approach is under question nowadays but Beijing rarely shows its political agenda beyond business and trade. It does have some military presence and a better arms exporter for region but it didn't go beyond to protect its trade and energy supply line. The fine lines remain to Beijing's non-interventionist approach and how it carries forward the same in the future.

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